
ExplainTS: a benchmark dataset of pretrained models and post-hoc explanations for time-series classification

Maciej Mozolewski^{1,2,*}, Szymon Bobek² and Grzegorz J. Nalepa²

¹Jagiellonian Human-Centered AI Lab, Mark Kac Center for Complex Systems Research, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland

²Department of Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence, Institute of Applied Computer Science, Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Applied Computer Science, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland

Correspondence*:
Maciej Mozolewski
m.mozolewski@uj.edu.pl

2 ABSTRACT

3 An important challenge for reproducible research on explainable AI (XAI) for time-series is the lack
4 of standardized benchmark resources. To address this, we introduce *ExplainTS*, a comprehensive
5 dataset comprising univariate and multivariate time-series, pretrained classifiers, and precomputed local
6 explanations. To our knowledge, it is the first large-scale open testbed that offers such a diverse collection
7 of frozen artifacts, enabling researchers to evaluate and compare XAI methods under strictly identical
8 conditions.

9 ExplainTS bundles 83 univariate and 20 multivariate datasets from the UCR/UEA archive, predefined
10 75/25 train–test splits, a unified ConvLSTM-based classifier per task, and precomputed outputs for four
11 model-agnostic explainers (SHAP, LIME, Anchor, Post-hoc Attribution Rules – PHAR), all stored as
12 NumPy arrays or rule records with companion Python code and notebooks, including an educational case
13 study demonstrating how to efficiently calculate quantitative XAI metrics, such as explanation stability,
14 directly from the artifacts.

15 Rather than imposing a single evaluation protocol, *ExplainTS* provides a non-prescriptive artifact layer
16 where researchers can benchmark custom metrics, such as stability or faithfulness, without the variance
17 or overhead of recomputation.

18 All *ExplainTS* resources are available under the CC-BY-4.0 license on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.15173400)
19 and GitHub (github.com/mozo64/papers/tree/main/zenodo-ucr). Designed as a living resource,
20 we actively invite community contributions to expand its collection of methods and metrics in future
21 releases.

22 **Keywords:** time-series classification, explainable AI, post-hoc explanations, SHAP, LIME, Anchor, Post-hoc Attribution Rules (PHAR),
23 benchmark dataset

1 INTRODUCTION

24 Reproducibility in machine learning (ML) traditionally relies on shared datasets and fixed train–test
25 splits. However, evaluating Explainable AI (XAI) introduces additional complexity, as explanations
26 depend on both the data and the specific underlying model. In time-series classification, where
27 complex black-box neural networks are increasingly deployed (Fawaz et al., 2020), the lack of
28 standardized XAI benchmarks (Höllig et al., 2023) severely hinders progress. Currently, most studies
29 retrain models and recompute explanations from scratch. This not only inflates computational costs
30 but also makes it nearly impossible to disentangle genuine XAI methodological improvements from
31 model variation, preprocessing differences, or the inherent run-to-run variance of perturbation-based
32 post-hoc explainers (Ribeiro et al., 2018).

33 To ensure reproducibility, we extend standard ML practices by treating datasets, trained
34 models, and explanation pipelines as fixed benchmark artifacts. While mature frameworks like
35 *aeon* (Middlehurst et al., 2024) standardize predictive evaluation, and dedicated XAI libraries enable
36 the calculation of explanations, they do not distribute precomputed, resource-intensive XAI outputs.
37 Providing this frozen baseline layer eliminates the computational overhead of recomputing ad hoc
38 explanations, enabling consistent XAI evaluation.

39 Beyond reproducibility, generating sampling-based explanations for time-series is often
40 computationally more expensive than training the models. While traditional ML repositories like
41 *OpenML* and the *UCR Time Series Classification Archive* successfully reduce redundant computation,
42 no equivalent initiative stores precomputed post-hoc explanations alongside underlying models for
43 diverse time-series tasks. Existing XAI frameworks, such as *Captum* (Kokhlikyan et al., 2020),
44 *Quantus* (Hedström et al., 2023), and *Alibi* (Klaise et al., 2021), offer valuable tooling but still
45 require resource-intensive model retraining and explanation recomputation.

46 Furthermore, while XAI evaluation datasets exist (Tritscher et al., 2020), particularly in vision and
47 NLP (Arras et al., 2022; DeYoung et al., 2020; Yalcin et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2025),
48 they focus on ground-truth annotations rather than reproducible *model plus explanation* pipelines.
49 Similarly, time-series benchmarks like *Exathlon* (Jacob et al., 2021) and *XTSC-Bench* (Höllig et al.,
50 2023) do not distribute precomputed post-hoc explanations. Unlike standalone software libraries,
51 *ExplainTS* acts as a complementary data resource. By providing frozen, ready-to-use explanation
52 artifacts it allows researchers to evaluate new XAI methods and metrics without the massive
53 computational burden of regenerating baselines.

54 Our main contribution is *ExplainTS*, a comprehensive repository comprising 103 diverse
55 classification tasks. Its core features include:

- 56 • Shared datasets, frozen train–test splits, and pretrained *ConvLSTM-based* baselines for consistent
57 evaluation of XAI methods.
- 58 • Precomputed outputs from multiple model-agnostic explainers (*SHAP* (Lundberg and Lee, 2017),
59 *LIME* (Ribeiro et al., 2016), *Anchor* (Ribeiro et al., 2018), and *PHAR* (Mozolewski et al., 2026)),
60 significantly reducing the computational cost of experiments and eliminating run-to-run stochastic
61 variance.
- 62 • A stable artifact layer (data, models, and explanations) for evaluating advanced explanation-
63 quality metrics (e.g., Lipschitz quotient or Jaccard Index) without re-running expensive pipelines.

64 • An educational case study and interactive templates demonstrating how to utilize these
65 precomputed artifacts for downstream XAI auditing, lowering the entry barrier for students
66 and researchers.

67 The repository structure (Figure 1) is fully extensible via open-source Python code
68 (github.com/mozo64/papers/tree/main/zenodo-ucr), allowing researchers to seamlessly
69 integrate their own custom metrics or algorithms without re-running expensive baseline pipelines. We
70 actively encourage the research community to contribute novel explainers and evaluation protocols
71 via pull requests, paving the way for collaborative, iterative updates to the Zenodo benchmark.

72 The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Sections 2 and 3 detail the benchmark
73 construction, data characteristics, and intended uses, while Section 3.4 outlines the Zenodo archive
74 structure. Importantly, comprehensive dataset statistics, exact model performance metrics, and
75 detailed repository layouts are provided exclusively in Supplementary Tables S1–S4.

2 METHODS

76 2.1 Datasets and preprocessing

77 The benchmark covers 103 tasks from the *UCR/UEA* time-series archives (Dau et al., 2019; Bagnall
78 et al., 2018), including 83 univariate and 20 multivariate datasets. We excluded datasets where the
79 standard ConvLSTM architecture failed to converge effectively, ensuring the repository contains
80 only reliable models for subsequent explanation analysis. The selected datasets vary significantly
81 in scale and complexity: total instance counts range from 30 to 24000 (median: 553), time-series
82 lengths span from 8 to 1751 time steps (median: 235), and the number of target classes varies
83 between 2 and 60 (median: 3). While univariate datasets contain a single channel, the multivariate
84 tasks include up to 144 dimensions. Detailed descriptive statistics for each individual dataset are
85 provided in Supplementary Tables S1–S3. Some multivariate tasks (e.g., *Libras*, *PenDigits*) originate
86 from the *UCI* Machine Learning Repository, but here we rely on the curated *UCR/UEA* variants
87 of these datasets¹. No new measurements were collected, and the original licensing terms for all
88 third-party datasets remain with their owners.

89 The raw time-series were downloaded programmatically using the *aeon* loader (Middlehurst
90 et al., 2024). Each channel was scaled to zero mean and unit variance with the scikit-learn
91 *StandardScaler* (Pedregosa et al., 2011) fitted to the training split and reused in the test split.
92 Each series of length T was segmented into blocks of shape $(n_{\text{steps}}, n_{\text{length}}, F)$, where n_{steps} is the
93 third-smallest divisor of T above 2 and F is the number of channels. This segmentation yields
94 tensors with a consistent shape, so that the same convolutional architecture can be instantiated
95 and trained separately on each data set, and converts each multichannel time-series into a $(\text{steps} \times$
96 $\text{length} \times \text{channels})$ representation compatible with the ConvLSTM-based implementation. While
97 this dynamic heuristic avoids per-dataset hyperparameter tuning and proved robust across the
98 majority of tasks, it represents a compromise. We did not perform a granular sensitivity analysis for
99 each dataset to quantify potential temporal distortions; however, maintaining a unified architecture
100 was prioritized to establish a stable baseline for XAI evaluation rather than maximizing predictive
101 performance through custom preprocessing. All datasets use a predefined stratified 75/25 train–test

¹ UCR/UEA archive: https://www.cs.ucr.edu/~eamonn/time_series_data_2018/ and <https://www.timeseriesclassification.com/>;
selected datasets (e.g., *PenDigits*) originate from UCI: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/>.

* M. Mozolewski, S. Bobek, G. J. Nalepa, "Explaining Time Series Classifiers with PHAR: Rule Extraction and Fusion from Post-hoc Attributions".

Figure 1. Repository overview: shared datasets in a common format, a pretrained deep classifier, and reference post-hoc explanations (SHAP, LIME, Anchor, PHAR).

102 split that is reused across all experiments. The accuracy of ConvLSTM-based classifier and the
 103 availability status of the SHAP, LIME, Anchor and PHAR explanations for all multivariate and
 104 univariate datasets are reported in Supplementary Tables S1–S3.

Figure 2. Overview of the ConvLSTM-based classifier used in ExplainTS, implemented with ConvLSTM1D layers on reshaped inputs, concluding with a Softmax output. Variables denote the original sequence length (T), number of features/channels (F), flattened representation size (N), and number of classes (C).

105 2.2 Classifier architecture and training

106 We employ a unified convolutional recurrent classifier architecture across all datasets. As illustrated
 107 in Figure 2, the model leverages stacked *ConvLSTM1D* layers applied to reshaped inputs to process
 108 time-series data.

109 The network consists of two such layers with 64 and 32 filters (kernel size 9, *ReLU* activations),
 110 followed by dropout (rate 0.5), flattening to a consistent-length representation N , a dense layer
 111 with 100 *ReLU* units, and a softmax output layer over the set of C target classes. The class
 112 imbalance is handled with class weights derived from the training labels. The models are trained
 113 with *Adam* (Kingma and Ba, 2015) and categorical cross-entropy for 25 epochs using a batch size of
 114 64. The same architecture and training protocol are applied across all tasks without per-dataset
 115 hyperparameter tuning, so that the model side remains constant and the analysis can focus on the
 116 behavior of post-hoc explainers².

117 While state-of-the-art models like ROCKET Dempster et al. (2020) and HIVE-COTE
 118 2.0 Middlehurst et al. (2021) excel in accuracy, their complex ensemble structures make perturbation-
 119 based XAI computationally prohibitive. Even with our standard ConvLSTM baseline, computing
 120 explanations using methods like DeepSHAP remains highly resource-intensive. Crucially, this fully
 121 differentiable architecture not only represents a typical deep learning black-box but also ensures
 122 future compatibility with gradient-based explainers.

² The training pipeline is available at: <https://github.com/mozo64/papers/blob/main/zenodo-ucr/notebooks/UCR-train.ipynb>

123 2.3 Explanation generation pipeline

124 For each trained *ConvLSTM*-based classifier, we generate post-hoc explanations using four model-
125 agnostic methods: *SHAP* (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) for additive feature attributions, *LIME* (Ribeiro
126 et al., 2016) for local surrogate models, *Anchor* (Ribeiro et al., 2018) for baseline rule-based
127 explanations, and our recently proposed *PHAR* framework (Mozolewski et al., 2026) for high-
128 coverage interval rules. These methods provide attribution-based and rule-based views of model
129 decisions.

130 To provide the community with standard, highly reproducible out-of-the-box baselines, SHAP,
131 LIME, and Anchor are deliberately executed without dataset-specific tuning.

132 *DeepSHAP* is executed using the reference Python implementation `shap.DeepExplainer`, utilizing
133 a background distribution of 1,000 random samples drawn from the training set. *LIME* uses
134 `LimeTabularExplainer` on flattened ($T \times C$) feature vectors (where T is the number of time steps
135 and C is the number of channels), configured with the default 5,000 perturbation samples and
136 continuous feature discretization (`discretize_continuous=True`) to ensure extraction stability³.

137 *Anchor* targets a 0.95 precision threshold with quartile discretization, using a grid-search heuristic
138 to maximize the product of coverage, precision, and condition count. To handle continuous
139 signals, it employs a multi-hour cascading retry mechanism, falling back from the `alibi` package
140 to `anchor-exp`⁴. Because Anchor frequently fails to extract valid rules despite this massive
141 computational budget, we integrated PHAR to guarantee stable, high-coverage rule generation
142 across the benchmark.

143 The PHAR pipeline inherently relies on a two-stage hyperparameter optimization (HPO) process
144 to extract robust rules⁵. First, a multi-objective Pareto-front search (implemented via the `optuna`
145 hyperparameter optimization framework) explores the optimal configuration (base explainer: SHAP
146 or LIME, threshold percentiles, and perturbation variance) on a small, stratified sample of the
147 test set, maximizing a trade-off between rule confidence and coverage while minimizing sparsity.
148 Second, the single best configuration is applied globally to extract robust interval rules for both the
149 full training and test splits. Consequently, alongside the final rules (formatted consistently with
150 Anchor records), the repository provides comprehensive metadata detailing the winning parameters
151 (`phar_metadata.json`) and the complete HPO trial history (`phar_trials_log.jsonl`), ensuring
152 full reproducibility of the extraction process.

153 SHAP and LIME explanations are stored as value arrays, while Anchor and PHAR explanations
154 are stored as JSON-like rule records with metadata fields such as *confidence* and *coverage* of
155 each individual rule. The listing 1 shows an example of an Anchor/PHAR rule record, where the
156 conjunction specifies the constraints at the feature-level, the *confidence* is the empirical precision of
157 the rule and the *coverage* is the fraction of the data set that satisfies it.

158 All training and explanation computations were run on two NVIDIA RTX A5500 GPUs. The same
159 explanation pipeline is applied across all datasets, which makes comparisons between explainers fair
160 and repeatable while still allowing users to rerun the methods with alternative settings (for example,

³ Reference implementations: github.com/shap/shap, github.com/marcotcr/lime. SHAP and LIME extraction: <https://github.com/mozo64/papers/blob/main/zenodo-ucr/notebooks/UCR-explainers-lime-shap.ipynb>

⁴ Reference implementations: github.com/marcotcr/anchor, github.com/SeldonIO/alibi. Anchor extraction: <https://github.com/mozo64/papers/blob/main/zenodo-ucr/notebooks/UCR-explainers-anchor.ipynb>

⁵ PHAR extraction: <https://github.com/mozo64/papers/blob/main/zenodo-ucr/notebooks/UCR-explainers-phar.ipynb>

161 different background sets or sampling budgets) on top of the predefined splits and pretrained models
 162 in the benchmark dataset.

163 **Listing 1.** Example Anchor rule record used in ExplainTS (PHAR follows the same schema)

```

164 [
165   {
166     "index": 123,
167     "success": true,
168     "prediction": "1",
169     "rule": {
170       "feature_1": [ ">-0.74", "<=-0.12" ],
171       "feature_11": [ ">3.94", "<=4.01" ],
172       "feature_110": [ ">1.89", "<=2.91" ]
173     },
174     "confidence": 0.9565,
175     "coverage": 0.7197
176   }
177 ]
  
```

179 2.4 Code repository

180 All notebooks and helper scripts used to build the ExplainTS benchmark dataset are hosted on a
 181 public GitHub repository ⁶. The main top-level directories are:

182 *notebooks*/ExplainTS_CaseStudy.ipynb (an educational case study calculating XAI stability
 183 metrics), UCR-train.ipynb (training ConvLSTM-based models), UCR-explainers-lime-shap.ipynb,
 184 UCR-explainers-anchor.ipynb, and UCR-explainers-phar.ipynb (running SHAP/LIME,
 185 Anchor, and PHAR explainers), and datasets_summary.ipynb (extracting dataset statistics
 186 and calculating model accuracies).

187 *services*/model_manager.py, model_server.py, and simple job-listing utilities used to parallelise
 188 explanation jobs for *Anchor*.

189 *results*/contains data_and_model_evaluations.csv with properties of the datasets, train/test
 190 splits and accuracies generated by the datasets_summary.ipynb notebook.

191 *scripts*/bash utilities for dataset assembly, including compress_models.sh and compress_explainers.sh
 192 (packaging models and individual artifacts), filter_move.sh (validating completeness and
 193 organizing bundles), compress_all.sh (creating the final Zenodo archives), and report.sh
 194 (generating coverage statistics).

195 These resources facilitate full reproducibility and provide templates for integrating new explainers.
 196 Detailed Zenodo archive structures and their exact contents are documented in *Supplementary*
 197 *Material* Section 1.2 and Table S4.

⁶ <https://github.com/mozo64/papers/tree/main/zenodo-ucr>.

3 BENCHMARK CHARACTERISTICS AND USAGE NOTES

198 We characterize the ExplainTS benchmark along two axes: the performance of a shared *ConvLSTM-*
199 *based classifier* baseline across datasets and the availability of post-hoc explanations (*DeepSHAP,*
200 *LIME, Anchor*) on the train and test splits.

201 3.1 Model performance and explanation availability

202 While SHAP achieves full coverage and LIME covers all except *FaceDetection*, Anchor rules
203 (exported with *confidence* and *coverage* metadata) successfully span only 4 of 20 multivariate and
204 26 of 83 univariate datasets. To overcome Anchor's inherent difficulty with continuous time-series,
205 we integrated the rule-based PHAR framework, which guarantees robust extraction and restores full
206 coverage across all 103 tasks.

207 Although our vanilla ConvLSTM baseline generally underperforms top UCR/UEA leaderboards,
208 these models remain highly valuable for XAI: their explanations faithfully expose internal logic,
209 allowing researchers to analyze structural flaws and debug misclassifications.

210 Dataset-specific metrics are detailed in Supplementary Tables S1–S3.

211 3.2 Educational demonstration and usage tutorial

212 To practically demonstrate the utility of the benchmark, we provide an educational template,
213 *ExplainTS_CaseStudy.ipynb*. Importantly, this script serves strictly as a technical proof-of-concept
214 and a usage tutorial, not as a comprehensive empirical evaluation of XAI methods. It illustrates a
215 plug-and-play workflow where users can seamlessly load a pretrained time-series classifier alongside
216 its test data to verify baseline classification accuracy. Subsequently, it shows how to fetch the
217 corresponding precomputed explanation artifacts, covering both continuous feature attributions
218 (*shap.zip, lime.zip*) and discrete, logic-based rules (*anchor.zip, phar.zip*). Furthermore, the notebook
219 demonstrates how to visualize these explanations directly over the raw time-series signals, including
220 helper routines for exporting publication-ready PDF figures, and provides example implementations
221 of quantitative XAI stability metrics, such as the Jaccard Index for rule agreement and the local
222 Lipschitz quotient for attribution robustness. By completely bypassing the computationally expensive
223 phases of model training and explainer optimization, this template highlights how researchers can use
224 the repository to immediately focus on prototyping custom metrics and advancing XAI evaluation.

225 3.3 Intended and typical uses of the ExplainTS benchmark

226 Since pretrained models and post-hoc explanations are precomputed for all tasks, the primary
227 use of the benchmark is to facilitate the evaluation of new explainer variants, explanation-quality
228 metrics, or visualization techniques without the overhead of repeating model training or explanation
229 sampling. The diversity of the 103 datasets further enables large-scale meta-analyses, allowing
230 researchers to investigate how data characteristics correlate with explanation properties. Users
231 can, for example, derive custom stability indicators for SHAP and LIME, filter Anchor and PHAR
232 rules by *confidence* and *coverage*, or conduct direct cross-method comparisons (e.g., contrasting
233 attribution maps with discrete logic rules). By freezing the data splits and model weights, *ExplainTS*
234 ensures that all such comparative experiments are strictly isolated from the underlying model and
235 run-to-run variance.

236 Furthermore, ExplainTS provides an accessible entry point for teaching and rapid prototyping. By
237 combining real-world datasets with a unified architecture and a public code repository (Section 2.4),
238 it significantly lowers the barrier to entry for applied XAI on time-series.

239 Users can rely on the provided educational notebooks, such as the demonstration discussed in the
240 previous section, as practical templates to load artifacts, experiment with visualizations, and safely
241 extend the benchmark with custom metrics or explainer implementations. Ultimately, *ExplainTS*
242 is designed as a living, community-driven resource; we strongly invite researchers to submit their
243 locally computed explanation artifacts to be incorporated into subsequent, jointly-authored releases
244 of the Zenodo record.

245 3.4 Limitations and future extensions of the benchmark

246 As a uniform benchmark, *ExplainTS* has several inherent limitations. Currently, precomputed
247 artifacts are restricted to four model-agnostic methods (*DeepSHAP*, *LIME*, *Anchor*, *PHAR*).
248 Although PHAR mitigates Anchor's coverage gaps, extracting discrete rules from continuous time-
249 series remains challenging; users must carefully account for the exported *confidence* and *coverage*
250 metadata. Furthermore, gradient-based (e.g., *Integrated Gradients*, *Grad-CAM*) and counterfactual
251 explainers are not yet included. To address this, we actively invite the research community to
252 contribute new explainers to the code repository, with the goal of incorporating community-generated
253 artifacts into future updates of the Zenodo record.

254 Second, lacking ground-truth relevance masks for real-world UCR/UEA data, evaluating
255 explanation faithfulness requires proxy metrics. Consequently, SHAP and LIME outputs must
256 be interpreted as perturbation-based approximations, not causal truths. Structurally, the current
257 benchmark is limited to classification tasks using a single ConvLSTM baseline. Future extensions
258 may include alternative architectures (e.g., *InceptionTime*, *Transformers*), forecasting tasks, and
259 reference implementations of cross-dataset XAI metrics.

260 Finally, the UCR/UEA archive exhibits domain imbalance (heavily dominated by sensor, motion,
261 and image data), potentially limiting XAI generalizability. Ethically, while *ExplainTS* lacks sensitive
262 data, deploying such post-hoc pipelines on real-world sequences (e.g., health records) requires strict
263 safeguards to prevent instance-level feature leakage via local explanations.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

264 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of commercial or financial
265 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

266 **Maciej Mozolewski:** Conceptualization; Software (computation of LIME numeric explanations;
267 rule mining with Anchor and PHAR); Educational notebook; Data curation (assembly of the
268 repository and file layout); Writing (introduction, methods, excluding data splitting and model
269 training; characterization of dataset; declarations and statements); Visualization (tables and figures);
270 Edition & Review.

271 **Szymon Bobek:** Conceptual guidance; Methods (data splitting scheme and model training protocol,
272 data set partitioning); Software (Model architecture and training, SHAP computation); Writing

273 (introduction, methods: data splitting and training), Edition & Review.
274 **Grzegorz J. Nalepa**: Conceptual guidance; Supervision; Edition & Review.

FUNDING

275 This paper is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon
276 Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement number 101120406. The
277 paper reflects only the authors' view, and the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made
278 of the information it contains.

279 The contribution of Maciej Mozolewski for the research for this publication has been supported
280 by a grant from the Priority Research Area (DigiWorld) under the Mark Kac Center for Complex
281 Systems Research Strategic Programme Excellence Initiative at Jagiellonian University.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

282 The authors thank the Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Applied Computer Science at Jagiellonian
283 University for computational resources.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

284 The *ExplainTS* artifacts are available at Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.15173400). The deposit includes:
285 *train_test.zip* (NumPy arrays, 75/25 split; original UCR/UEA licenses apply); *models.zip* (TensorFlow
286 SavedModels and .h5 files for loading flexibility); and explanation archives: *shap.zip* and *lime.zip*
287 (NumPy arrays), *anchor.zip* (JSON rule sets with metadata), and *phar.zip* (JSON rules, plus `.jsonl`
288 hyperoptimization histories and final best `.json` results). Please cite the DOI upon reuse.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

289 During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used *ChatGPT* and *Gemini Pro* to refine the
290 language, improve readability, and check grammatical consistency, and draft selected code snippets,
291 typing, and docstrings. All such suggestions and code were reviewed, tested, and, when needed,
292 rewritten by the authors, who assume full responsibility for the final text and software. Those tools
293 did not generate any numerical results, metrics, tables, or figures; all results were obtained by
294 running our code on the described data and models.

REFERENCES

- 295 Arras, L., Osman, A., and Samek, W. (2022). Clevr-xai: A benchmark dataset for the ground
296 truth evaluation of neural network explanations. *Information Fusion* 81, 14–40. doi:https:
297 //doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2021.11.008
- 298 Bagnall, A., Dau, H. A., Lines, J., Flynn, M., Large, J., Bostrom, A., et al. (2018). The UEA
299 multivariate time series classification archive, 2018. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.00075*
- 300 Dau, H. A., Bagnall, A., Kamgar, K., Yeh, C.-C. M., Zhu, Y., Gharghabi, S., et al. (2019). The ucr
301 time series archive. *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica* 6, 1293–1305. doi:10.1109/JAS.
302 2019.1911747

- 303 Dempster, A., Petitjean, F., and Webb, G. I. (2020). Rocket: exceptionally fast and accurate time
304 series classification using random convolutional kernels. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*
305 34, 1454–1495
- 306 DeYoung, J., Jain, S., Rajani, N. F., Lehman, E., Xiong, C., Socher, R., et al. (2020). Eraser: A
307 benchmark to evaluate rationalized nlp models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.03429*
- 308 Fawaz, H. I., Lucas, B., Forestier, G., Pelletier, C., Schmidt, D. F., Weber, J., et al. (2020).
309 Inceptiontime: Finding alexnet for time series classification. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*
310 34, 1936–1962. doi:10.1007/s10618-020-00710-y
- 311 Hedström, A., Weber, L., Krakowczyk, D., Bareeva, D., Motzkus, F., Samek, W., et al. (2023).
312 Quantus: An explainable ai toolkit for responsible evaluation of neural network explanations and
313 beyond. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 24, 1–11
- 314 Höllig, J., Thoma, S., and Grimm, F. (2023). Xtsc-bench: Quantitative benchmarking for explainers
315 on time series classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.14957*
- 316 Jacob, V., Song, F., Stiegler, A., Rad, B., Diao, Y., and Tatbul, N. (2021). Exathlon: A benchmark
317 for explainable anomaly detection over time series. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.05073*
- 318 Kingma, D. P. and Ba, J. (2015). Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *International*
319 *Conference on Learning Representations* ArXiv:1412.6980
- 320 Klaise, J., Van Looveren, A., Vacanti, G., and Coca, A. (2021). Alibi explain: Algorithms for
321 explaining machine learning models. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 22, 1–7
- 322 Kokhlikyan, N., Miglani, V., Martin, M., Wang, E., Alsallakh, B., Reynolds, J., et al.
323 (2020). Captum: A unified and generic model interpretability library for pytorch. *arXiv Cite*
324 *arxiv:2009.07896*
- 325 Liu, Y., Khandagale, S., White, C., and Neiswanger, W. (2021). Synthetic benchmarks for scientific
326 research in explainable machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.12543*
- 327 Lundberg, S. M. and Lee, S.-I. (2017). A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. In
328 *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems* (Red
329 Hook, NY, USA: Curran Associates Inc.), NIPS'17, 4768–4777
- 330 Middlehurst, M., Ismail-Fawaz, A., Guillaume, A., Holder, C., Guijo-Rubio, D., Bulatova, G., et al.
331 (2024). aeon: a python toolkit for learning from time series. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*
332 25, 1–10
- 333 Middlehurst, M., Large, J., Flynn, M., Lines, J., Bostrom, A., and Bagnall, A. (2021). Hive-cote
334 2.0: a new meta ensemble for time series classification. *Machine Learning* 110, 3211–3243
- 335 Mozolewski, M., Bobek, S., and Nalepa, G. J. (2026). Explaining time series classifiers with PHAR:
336 Rule extraction and fusion from post-hoc attributions
- 337 Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., et al. (2011).
338 Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 12, 2825–2830
- 339 Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., and Guestrin, C. (2016). "why should i trust you?": Explaining the
340 predictions of any classifier. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference*
341 *on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing
342 Machinery), KDD '16, 1135–1144. doi:10.1145/2939672.2939778
- 343 Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., and Guestrin, C. (2018). Anchors: High-precision model-agnostic
344 explanations. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* 32. doi:10.1609/aaai.
345 v32i1.11491
- 346 Tritscher, J., Ring, M., Schlr, D., Hettlinger, L., and Hotho, A. (2020). Evaluation of post-hoc xai
347 approaches through synthetic tabular data. In *Foundations of Intelligent Systems*, eds. D. Helic,

- 348 G. Leitner, M. Stettinger, A. Felfernig, and Z. W. Raś. Springer (Cham: Springer International
349 Publishing), 422–430
- 350 Yalcin, O., Fan, X., and Liu, S. (2021). Evaluating the correctness of explainable ai algorithms for
351 classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2105.09740*
- 352 Zhang, Y., Song, J., Gu, S., Jiang, T., Pan, B., Bai, G., et al. (2025). Saliency-bench: A
353 comprehensive benchmark for evaluating visual explanations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.08537*